

STUDENTS' PERSONAL CHALLENGES AND ITS IMPACT ON THEIR ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the perceived personal challenges faced by students and their impact on academic performance. Key findings revealed that financial concerns, academic pressure, and family issues significantly affected students' well-being and performance. Financial stress emerged as a significant challenge, often reducing study time and lower productivity. Academic concerns, such as pressure to achieve high grades and test anxiety, were also prevalent, contributing to stress and decreased performance in tasks and exams. Family dynamics, including financial instability and emotional strain, further influenced students' focus and motivation. Although suicidal ideation was rarely reported, its presence underscored the need for mental health support. Statistical analysis showed significant positive correlations between personal challenges and declines in academic performance across tasks, written assignments, and important exams, bringing out the critical impact of financial, academic, and family-related stressors on students' outcomes. Such findings highlighted the need to implement targeted interventions that can support students' academic and personal well-being.

Keywords: *personal challenges, academic performance, financial concern, academic concern, family concerns, suicidal ideation*

INTRODUCTION

To successfully compete in the prevailing dynamic industrial environment, students are not only supposed to develop their knowledge but are also expected to have imperative skills and abilities (Aamir, 2021). Aafreen et al. (2018) stated that students continuously experience pressure from different sources during academic life, which ultimately causes stress among students. When the stress becomes chronic or exceeds a certain level, it affects an individual's mental health and may lead to different psychological disorders, such as depression (Schimelpfening, 2020). There can be several reasons for this: family issues, exposure to a new lifestyle in colleges and universities, poor academic grades, teacher favoritism, etc. Never-ending stress or academic pressure from studies can also be a chief reason leading to depression in students (Akinola et al., 2019). Ardalan (2021) conducted a study in the United States (US). It was reported that depression is a common issue among students in the US, and 20 percent of them may have a depressive disorder spanning 12 months or more. It affects students' mental and physical health and limits their social relationships and professional careers.

According to Dagdag, et al. (2019), around 9% to 23% of students in higher education institutions in the Philippines face challenges in various areas, including academic, social, family, emotional, personal, financial, and spiritual aspects, with the severity ranging from moderate to great extent. These issues highlight lapses in teachers' classroom management and pedagogy, as well as the lack of activities aimed at fostering students' holistic development and effective learning habits.

In the current highly competitive academic environment, students' performance is affected mainly by several factors, such as social media, academic quality, family and social bonding, and more (Likisa, 2018). While this study highlights the challenges students face and their impact on academic performance, a significant gap exists in understanding how these factors are influenced by institutional support systems, particularly in this institution.

The researchers addressed this issue to understand students' various personal challenges and how they influenced their academic performance. By examining factors such as financial concerns, academic concern, family dynamics, and other personal challenges, the researchers aimed to uncover correlations between these factors and students' academic success or struggles. This study seeks to provide insights that can help educators, policymakers, and this institution develop strategies to support students holistically and promote effective learning and well-being.

Research Questions

This study aimed to identify students' challenges and implications on academic performance. Its focus is on understanding how said challenges impact the ability to succeed academically and participate in school activities.

It particularly aspires to answer the questions:

1. What do students perceive as personal challenges they encounter in terms of the following areas:
 - 1.1 Financial Concern;
 - 1.2 Academic Concern;
 - 1.3 Family Concerns; and,
 - 1.4 Suicidal Ideation?
2. To what extent do personal challenges of students affect their academic performance in terms of:
 - 2.1 Performance Task;
 - 2.2 Written Task; and,
 - 2.3 Major Examinations?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived personal challenges of students and the extent to which these challenges impact their academic performance?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive-correlational survey. It was descriptive because it (a) described the perceived personal challenges encountered by the students and (b) evaluated the impact of students' challenges on their academic performance. On the other hand, this study was correlational because the mentioned variables were correlated.

Research Respondents

The respondents of the study were the baccalaureate students of Metro Dumaguete College enrolled in baccalaureate courses for the academic year 2024-2025. Of the 146 total population of the 6 courses, 109 were the sampled students. These students were chosen through random sampling, wherein every second person in the student list was selected. The distribution of the number of third-year baccalaureate students who participated was shown below:

Course	Population	Sample
BTVTED	9	7
BSTM	44	33
BSIT	34	25
BSCS	12	9
BSBA – MM	19	14
BSBA – FM	28	21
Total	146	109

Research Instrument

A researcher-made questionnaire was used in the study. The questionnaire was pilot-tested on 30 students before conducting the actual study to ensure reliability and validity. The questionnaire was presented to three experts in the field of education.

Research Procedure

After the research proposal, the researchers integrated all the corrections and suggestions of the panel members. A letter of request to conduct the study was sent to the Metro Dumaguete College President upon the approval of the College of Arts and Education Assistant Dean. Afterward, the signed and approved letter of request to administer the questionnaire was sent to the MDC registrar, requesting the class list.

The signed and approved request was presented to the program chairs and students' advisers. During the distribution, the researcher explained to the students the purpose and importance of the research. The questionnaires were retrieved right after the students had answered the questions. The results were then tallied using MS Excel and Megastar software and were analyzed and interpreted by an expert statistician.

RESULTS

Table 1.1 Perceived Personal Challenges Encountered by the Students in terms of Financial Concerns ($n = 109$)

Financial Concerns	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1. I'm experiencing stress from balancing my academic responsibilities with the need to earn money, which negatively impacts my grades.	3.47	Often
2. I'm dealing with the pressure of supporting my family financially while also trying to succeed academically.	2.97	Sometimes
3. I'm often anxious about meeting my financial obligations, which affects my overall mental well-being and academic focus.	3.14	Sometimes
4. I'm working to fund my finances, which has reduced my study time and made it harder to focus and manage my academic workload.	2.87	Sometimes
5. I'm finding it hard to purchase the latest technology/software and project required for my courses, affecting my ability to complete assignments.	3.09	Sometimes
Composite	3.11	Sometimes
Legend	Scale	Verbal Description
	4.21 – 5.00	Always
	3.41 – 4.20	Often
	2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes
	1.81 – 2.60	Rarely
	1.00 – 1.80	Never

The data in Table 1.1 reveal that financial concerns significantly impact students' academic performance and well-being, with a composite mean of 3.11 ("Sometimes"). The most pressing issue, with a weighted mean of 3.47 ("Often"), is the stress of

balancing academic responsibilities with the need to earn money, which negatively affects students' grades. This finding aligns with studies by Usman et al. (2019), which emphasize that financial stress often leads to lower academic performance and reduced credit hours. Additionally, students report anxiety about meeting financial obligations (mean of 3.14) and difficulty acquiring necessary technology or software for assignments (mean of 3.09), reflecting the challenges faced by underprivileged families in supporting educational needs, as highlighted by Asri et al. (2020).

Table 1.2 Perceived Personal Challenges Encountered by the Students in terms of Academic Concerns (n = 109)

Academic Concern	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1. I'm struggling to balance my schoolwork with extracurricular activities, leading to increased stress and lower performance.	3.03	Sometimes
2. I'm experiencing anxiety before tests, which causes me to forget what I've studied and perform poorly.	3.10	Sometimes
3. I'm feeling pressured to achieve high grades, which is making me feel burned out and less motivated.	3.54	Often
4. I'm dealing with constant pressure to perform well from my parents and teachers, which makes studying feel like a burden.	3.26	Sometimes
5. I'm unable to focus during study sessions because my mind is constantly occupied with worries about my academic performance.	3.38	Sometimes
Composite	3.26	Sometimes

Legend	Scale	Verbal Description
	4.21 – 5.00	Always
	3.41 – 4.20	Often
	2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes
	1.81 – 2.60	Rarely
	1.00 – 1.80	Never

The data in Table 1.2 highlight the significant academic concerns experienced by students, with a composite mean of 3.26 ("Sometimes"). The highest-rated concern, with a weighted mean of 3.54 ("Often"), is the pressure to achieve high grades, which leads to burnout and reduced motivation. This aligns with studies by Chitrakar and P.M. (2023) and Travis et al. (2020), which emphasize that excessive academic pressures can negatively impact students' mental health and motivation. Anxiety before tests (mean of 3.10) and struggles to balance schoolwork with extracurricular activities (mean of 3.03) further illustrate the challenges students face in managing their academic and personal commitments. The constant worry about performance, rated at 3.38, also points to a pervasive mental burden affecting students' focus and productivity.

Table 1.3 Perceived Personal Challenges Encountered by the Students in terms of Family Concerns (n = 109)

Family Concerns	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1. I'm struggling to concentrate on my studies because of conflicts and arguments at home.	2.74	Sometimes
2. I'm often distracted in class thinking about the financial problems my family is facing.	3.07	Sometimes

3. I'm feeling emotionally drained by the tension at home, and it's affecting my motivation to do well in school.	2.85	Sometimes
4. I'm experiencing the effects of not having parental support and guidance, which is impacting my academic decisions and performance.	2.50	Rarely
5. I'm struggling with motivation because the instability at home makes it difficult to see the importance of academic success.	2.52	Rarely
Composite	2.74	Sometimes
Legend	Scale	Verbal Description
	4.21 – 5.00	Always
	3.41 – 4.20	Often
	2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes
	1.81 – 2.60	Rarely
	1.00 – 1.80	Never

Table 1.3 shows that family concerns, such as conflicts at home, financial challenges, and lack of parental support, are significant factors affecting students' academic performance and mental well-being. The composite mean of 2.74, corresponding to "Sometimes," indicates that while these challenges are not constant, they are frequent enough to disrupt students' academic focus and motivation. Specifically, financial difficulties (mean = 3.07) and emotional stress from family conflicts (mean = 2.85) were among the most notable issues faced by students.

Table 1.4 Perceived Personal Challenges Encountered by the Students in terms of Suicidal Ideation (n = 109)

Suicidal Ideation	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1. I have experienced thoughts of wanting to end my life due to stress related to academic performance.	2.32	Rarely
2. The thought of suicide has crossed my mind when facing overwhelming challenges in my studies.	2.08	Rarely
3. I have thought about ending my life because I feel hopeless about my academic future.	2.16	Rarely
4. I have imagined what it would be like to no longer exist because of the challenges I face in my studies.	2.28	Rarely
5. I have had moments where I felt like giving up on life because of difficulties in my academic pursuits.	2.42	Rarely
Composite	2.25	Rarely
Legend	Scale	Verbal Description
	4.21 – 5.00	Always
	3.41 – 4.20	Often
	2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes
	1.81 – 2.60	Rarely
	1.00 – 1.80	Never

Table 1.4 reveals a relatively low frequency of such thoughts, with a composite mean of 2.25, categorized as "Rarely." This suggests that while some students experience fleeting thoughts of suicide related to academic stress, these instances are not widespread. The individual items, such as thoughts of ending life due to academic stress (2.32), feeling hopeless about the academic future (2.16), and imagining non-existence because of academic challenges (2.28), all fall under the "Rarely" category, further indicating that such ideations are not common among the students surveyed.

Table 2.1 Extent of Students' Personal Challenges affecting their Academic Performance in terms of Performance Task (n = 109)

Performance Task		$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1.	I am balancing personal issues with academic responsibilities often leads to a decline in my performance.	3.16	Sometimes
2.	I find it difficult to perform well academically when dealing with significant personal challenges.	3.27	Sometimes
3.	I am managing personal difficulties negatively affects my productivity and efficiency in completing academic assignments.	3.19	Sometimes
4.	I find it hard to engage effectively in academic activities when confronted with personal difficulties.	3.21	Sometimes
5.	I'm dealing with personal issues often leads to a decline in the quality of my academic work.	3.05	Sometimes
Composite		3.17	Sometimes
Legend	Scale	Verbal Description	
	4.21 – 5.00	Always	
	3.41 – 4.20	Often	
	2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes	
	1.81 – 2.60	Rarely	
	1.00 – 1.80	Never	

Table 2.1 shows that students' personal challenges affecting their academic performance, particularly in relation to performance tasks, shows that personal issues do impact academic output. The composite mean of 3.17, categorized as "Sometimes," indicates that students often experience difficulty in balancing personal challenges with academic responsibilities. The individual items also support this, with students reporting a "Sometimes" frequency in issues such as balancing personal difficulties with academic tasks (3.16), managing personal problems affecting productivity (3.19), and difficulty engaging in academic activities (3.21). These findings reflect a common challenge in education, where personal struggles can detract from a student's academic performance.

Table 2.2 Extent of Students' Personal Challenges affecting their Academic Performance in terms of Written Task (n = 109)

Written Task		$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1.	Balancing personal issues with written assignments often leads to a decline in my performance.	2.97	Sometimes
2.	I struggle to maintain consistent quality in my written work when facing personal challenges.	2.97	Sometimes
3.	My academic performance in written tasks is significantly impacted when I am dealing with personal challenges.	2.98	Sometimes
4.	I find it hard to engage creatively and analytically in writing when confronted with personal difficulties.	3.06	Sometimes
5.	When facing personal challenges, I struggle to maintain the same level of clarity and precision in my writing.	3.21	Sometimes
Composite		3.04	Sometimes
Legend	Scale	Verbal Description	
	4.21 – 5.00	Always	
	3.41 – 4.20	Often	
	2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes	
	1.81 – 2.60	Rarely	
	1.00 – 1.80	Never	

Table 2.2 shows that students' personal challenges affecting their academic performance in written tasks reveals that personal issues impact their ability to complete assignments effectively. The composite mean of 3.04, categorized as "Sometimes," suggests that students often struggle with balancing personal challenges and their written academic responsibilities. The individual responses show that students experience difficulty maintaining quality in their written work (2.97) and engaging creatively or analytically (3.06) when faced with personal difficulties. The highest score (3.21) is observed in the struggle to maintain clarity and precision in writing during challenging times.

Table 2.3 Extent of Students' Personal Challenges affecting their Academic Performance in terms of Major Examination (n = 109)

Major Examination	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1. I find it difficult to retain information and recall concepts during major exams when dealing with significant personal challenges.	3.38	Sometimes
2. I experience a lack of motivation to study effectively for major exams when I'm facing significant personal difficulties.	3.28	Sometimes
3. I find it difficult to concentrate and stay focused on exam material when personal difficulties are weighing heavily on my mind.	3.5	Often
4. I've observed that my performance in major exams tends to suffer in terms of accuracy and thoroughness when I'm dealing with personal hardships.	3.39	Sometimes
5. I find it challenging to maintain the same level of academic performance during major exams when I'm dealing with personal issues.	3.39	Sometimes
Composite	3.39	Sometimes
Legend	Scale	Verbal Description
	4.21 – 5.00	Always
	3.41 – 4.20	Often
	2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes
	1.81 – 2.60	Rarely
	1.00 – 1.80	Never

Table 2.3 shows data on students' personal challenges affecting their academic performance in major examinations revealing that personal difficulties often hinder their ability to perform well. The composite mean of 3.39, categorized as "Sometimes," indicates that students frequently struggle with maintaining their focus and performance during exams when facing personal challenges. Specifically, students find it difficult to concentrate (3.5) and retain information (3.38), and their performance in major exams tends to suffer in terms of accuracy and thoroughness (3.39).

Table 3.1 Relationship between the Students' Financial Concerns and the Extent affecting their Academic Performance

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Financial Concerns				
Performance Task	0.478	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Written Task	0.429	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Major Examination	0.443	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant

The data in Table 3.1 show a significant relationship between financial concerns and the extent to which they affect students' academic performance across various tasks, including performance tasks, written tasks, and major examinations. Pearson's correlation coefficients (r-values) of 0.478, 0.429, and 0.443 for each respective task ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) suggest that financial concerns strongly influence students' academic outcomes. This aligns with research indicating that financial stress is a major factor affecting students' academic performance. Financial difficulties can limit students' access to resources, extracurricular activities and even affect their mental health, leading to lower grades and academic struggles (Hamilton et al., 2019; Usman et al., 2019).

Table 3.2 Relationship between the Students' Academic Concerns and the Extent affecting their Academic Performance

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Academic Concerns				
Performance Task	0.509	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Written Task	0.513	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Major Examination	0.635	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant

Table 3.2 shows a significant relationship between academic concerns (such as performance tasks, written tasks, and major examinations) and their impact on students' academic performance. Pearson correlation coefficients ($r = 0.509$ for performance tasks, $r = 0.513$ for written tasks, and $r = 0.635$ for major examinations) indicate moderate to strong positive correlations, suggesting that as students' academic concerns increase, their academic performance is also affected. The ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) in each case confirm the statistical significance of these relationships.

Table 3.3 Relationship between the Students' Family Concerns and the Extent affecting their Academic Performance

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Family Concerns				
Performance Task	0.676	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Written Task	0.597	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Major Examination	0.614	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant

Table 3.3 shows that family concerns significantly affect students' academic performance since all of its strong positive correlations with performance tasks ($r = 0.676$), written tasks ($r = 0.597$), and major examinations ($r = 0.614$), respectively ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$), which means that the more students perceive their family concerns as more prevalent, the worse the level of impact on their academic outcomes on Family issues, be it financial stress, emotional pressure, or lack of support, have been quite well documented in literature to be a stressor preventing academic success (Deng et al., 2022; Zakaria, 2023; Hamilton et al., 2019).

Table 3.4 Relationship between the Students' Suicidal Ideation and the Extent affecting their Academic Performance

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Suicidal Ideation				
Performance Task	0.470	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Written Task	0.394	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Major Examination	0.452	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant

The data in Table 3.4 show a significant relationship between students' suicidal ideation and the extent to which it affects their academic performance. The positive Pearson correlation coefficients indicate that higher levels of suicidal thoughts are associated with a decline in academic performance across all areas. Specifically, the correlation values for performance tasks (0.470), written tasks (0.394), and major examinations (0.452) suggest moderate to strong relationships. The ($p = 0.00 < 0.05$) for each variable indicate that these relationships are statistically significant, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_{01}). This means that suicidal ideation has a significant impact on students' ability to perform academically. This is evident from the high Pearson correlation values and low p-values, which indicate that students experiencing suicidal thoughts tend to have lower academic performance across these areas.

DISCUSSION

Perceived Personal Challenges Encountered by the Students in terms of Financial Concerns

Table 1.1 reveal that financial concerns significantly impact students' academic performance and well-being, with a composite mean of 3.11 ("Sometimes"). The most pressing issue, with a weighted mean of 3.47 ("Often"), is the stress of balancing academic responsibilities with the need to earn money, which negatively affects students' grades. This finding aligns with studies by Usman et al. (2019), which emphasize that financial stress often leads to lower academic performance and reduced credit hours. Additionally, students report anxiety about meeting financial obligations (mean of 3.14) and difficulty acquiring necessary technology or software for assignments (mean of 3.09), reflecting the challenges faced by underprivileged families in supporting educational needs, as highlighted by Asri et al. (2020).

Financial difficulties can also force students to reduce their course loads or pause their studies, further delaying academic progress and increasing financial burdens on families, as noted by Norazlan et al. (2020). These issues underscore the need for accessible financial support systems, such as grants or scholarships, to mitigate the adverse effects of financial stress on academic outcomes. Financial stress not only disrupts students' focus and time management but also creates long-term challenges in achieving educational goals.

Perceived Personal Challenges Encountered by the Students in terms of Academic Concerns

Table 1.2 highlight the significant academic concerns experienced by students, with a composite mean of 3.26 ("Sometimes"). The highest-rated concern, with a weighted mean of 3.54 ("Often"), is the pressure to achieve high grades, which leads to burnout and reduced motivation. This aligns with studies by Chitrakar and P.M. (2023) and Travis et al. (2020), which emphasize that excessive academic pressures can negatively impact students' mental health and motivation. Anxiety before tests (mean of 3.10) and struggles to balance schoolwork with extracurricular activities (mean of 3.03) further illustrate the challenges students face in managing their academic and personal commitments. The constant worry about performance, rated at 3.38, also points to a pervasive mental burden affecting students' focus and productivity.

Research supports these findings, emphasizing that academic stress is one of the most prevalent stressors among students, often leading to mental health challenges like anxiety and depression (Austria-Cruz, 2019; Khan et al., 2022). Effective teaching strategies, clear communication, and engaging methods are crucial for mitigating these stressors, as they help improve understanding and student engagement (Khair & Misnawati, 2022; Li, 2023). Moreover, the influence of peer relationships, whether positive or negative, significantly shapes students' motivation and sense of belonging, which are critical for academic success (Allen et al., 2021; Wentzel, 2022). Students are grappling with academic stress and external expectations, which highlight the need for schools to foster a more supportive learning environment.

Perceived Personal Challenges Encountered by the Students in terms of Family Concerns

Table 1.3 shows that family concerns, such as conflicts at home, financial challenges, and lack of parental support, are significant factors affecting students' academic performance and mental well-being. The composite mean of 2.74, corresponding to "Sometimes," indicates that while these challenges are not constant, they are frequent enough to disrupt students' academic focus and motivation. Specifically, financial difficulties (mean = 3.07) and emotional stress from family conflicts (mean = 2.85) were among the most notable issues faced by students.

Research supports these findings, highlighting that family environments significantly shape students' academic outcomes. Wang et al. (2022) emphasize that a supportive family environment positively influences learning attitudes, while parental involvement and encouragement are critical predictors of academic success. Conversely, negative family dynamics, such as conflicts or financial instability, can hinder motivation and lead to emotional exhaustion, affecting students' academic decisions and performance (Mudzakir et al., 2024).

Further, parenting styles and socioeconomic factors also play a pivotal role in academic achievement. Creating a balanced and supportive home environment is crucial.

According to the Bay Atlantic University (2022), parents should focus on fostering their children's strengths, providing encouragement, and avoiding excessive academic pressure. Families with stable structures and effective communication tend to produce students with higher academic achievement (Liu, 2021). Conversely, students from broken families or those experiencing familial instability are more vulnerable to emotional and academic challenges (Sparks et al., 2021).

Perceived Personal Challenges Encountered by the Students in terms of Suicidal Ideation

Table 1.4 reveals a relatively low frequency of such thoughts, with a composite mean of 2.25, categorized as "Rarely." This suggests that while some students experience fleeting thoughts of suicide related to academic stress, these instances are not widespread. The individual items, such as thoughts of ending life due to academic stress (2.32), feeling hopeless about the academic future (2.16), and imagining non-existence because of academic challenges (2.28), all fall under the "Rarely" category, further indicating that such ideations are not common among the students surveyed.

The findings align with previous research, which suggests that although mental health issues, including suicidal ideation, are prevalent in college and academic settings (Chen et al., 2019; Mathewson, 2020), the incidence of suicidal thoughts is often inversely related to academic performance. Studies show that students with higher academic performance tend to report lower rates of suicidal ideation. The inverse relationship indicates that academic success, or at least a perception of academic competence, provides students with a sense of purpose and hope, potentially mitigating feelings of hopelessness or desperation associated with academic struggles (Ghorbanpour et al., 2024).

Extent of Students' Personal Challenges affecting their Academic Performance in terms of Performance Task

Table 2.1 shows that students' personal challenges affecting their academic performance, particularly in relation to performance tasks, shows that personal issues do impact academic output. The composite mean of 3.17, categorized as "Sometimes," indicates that students often experience difficulty in balancing personal challenges with academic responsibilities. The individual items also support this, with students reporting a "Sometimes" frequency in issues such as balancing personal difficulties with academic tasks (3.16), managing personal problems affecting productivity (3.19), and difficulty engaging in academic activities (3.21). These findings reflect a common challenge in education, where personal struggles can detract from a student's academic performance.

This aligns with research that highlights the influence of personal and emotional challenges on academic success. According to Howard (2019), students' emotional well-being and motivation are closely linked to their academic performance, as personal difficulties can create barriers to learning. Similarly, studies by Farley et al. (2019) suggest

that internal factors, like emotional distress, coupled with external challenges, like a lack of support, can significantly impact students' academic outcomes. Furthermore, personal difficulties, such as family issues or financial stress, can lead to lower productivity and efficiency, as confirmed by Duffy et al. (2021), who found that planning and executing tasks are major areas where students struggle when faced with personal challenges.

In line with González-Arias et al. (2023), students' academic performance is influenced by their ability to stay motivated and engage with their learning despite personal struggles. A positive mindset and resilience can mitigate some of these challenges, but when personal issues are overwhelming, students may find it difficult to perform well academically, as indicated by the data.

Extent of Students' Personal Challenges affecting their Academic Performance in terms of Written Task

Table 2.2 shows that students' personal challenges affecting their academic performance in written tasks reveals that personal issues impact their ability to complete assignments effectively. The composite mean of 3.04, categorized as "Sometimes," suggests that students often struggle with balancing personal challenges and their written academic responsibilities. The individual responses show that students experience difficulty maintaining quality in their written work (2.97) and engaging creatively or analytically (3.06) when faced with personal difficulties. The highest score (3.21) is observed in the struggle to maintain clarity and precision in writing during challenging times.

These results align with existing research highlighting the strong connection between personal challenges and academic performance. According to Howard (2019), emotional well-being and motivation are closely tied to academic success, with students facing personal difficulties often experiencing a decline in performance. This is further supported by Farley et al. (2019), who argue that both internal and external factors, such as cognitive abilities and socio-economic status, influence students' academic outcomes. Personal struggles can create cognitive overload, making it harder for students to focus and produce high-quality work.

In addition, studies such as those by Alqurashi (2021) emphasize that students' learning environments, including the emotional and social context, play a significant role in academic achievement. When students deal with stressors like family issues or financial concerns, it affects their ability to plan, execute, and follow through on tasks effectively, as shown by Duffy et al. (2021). These challenges often lead to issues in task completion, poor time management, and lower-quality academic outputs.

Moreover, González-Arias et al. (2023) note that students who actively engage with their academic work are more likely to perform well, but personal challenges can reduce this engagement. The combination of emotional stress, pressure, and external difficulties can hinder students' creativity, clarity, and analytical abilities, resulting in subpar written tasks.

Extent of Students' Personal Challenges affecting their Academic Performance in terms of Major Examination

Table 2.3 shows data on students' personal challenges affecting their academic performance in major examinations revealing that personal difficulties often hinder their ability to perform well. The composite mean of 3.39, categorized as "Sometimes," indicates that students frequently struggle with maintaining their focus and performance during exams when facing personal challenges. Specifically, students find it difficult to concentrate (3.5) and retain information (3.38), and their performance in major exams tends to suffer in terms of accuracy and thoroughness (3.39).

These findings are consistent with existing research that shows personal difficulties can significantly impact academic performance. For instance, Howard (2019) emphasizes the importance of understanding various factors, including personal challenges, that influence academic outcomes. Emotional well-being, motivation, and focus are all critical components of academic performance, and personal challenges often disrupt these factors. Farley et al. (2019) further explain that when students face personal hardships, such as family issues or mental health struggles, their ability to concentrate, retain information, and stay motivated can decrease, leading to poorer exam performance.

Moreover, the challenges of studying for major exams while dealing with personal difficulties align with findings by Duffy et al. (2021), who note that the planning, execution, and consequences of tasks are often affected by external factors like personal stress. Stress and lack of motivation can hinder students' ability to prepare effectively, which is reflected in their struggle with exam performance. Studies by Popa-Velea et al. (2021) and Abbas & Sagsan (2019) highlight the physical and psychological consequences of stress, such as fatigue and difficulty concentrating, which can worsen during periods of personal challenges.

Relationship between the Students' Financial Concerns and the Extent affecting their Academic Performance

Table 3.1 show a significant relationship between financial concerns and the extent to which they affect students' academic performance across various tasks, including performance tasks, written tasks, and major examinations. Pearson's correlation coefficients (r-values) of 0.478, 0.429, and 0.443 for each respective task ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) suggest that financial concerns strongly influence students' academic outcomes. This aligns with research indicating that financial stress is a major factor affecting students' academic performance. Financial difficulties can limit students' access to resources, extracurricular activities and even affect their mental health, leading to lower grades and academic struggles (Hamilton et al., 2019; Usman et al., 2019).

Moreover, personal challenges such as family issues, academic stress, and peer influences can compound the negative impact of financial concerns. Studies have shown that students from low-income families often face additional obstacles, including

inadequate academic support and the need to balance part-time work, which detracts from their studies (Deng et al., 2022). These students tend to experience higher stress levels and have poorer academic performance (Norazlan et al., 2020). Financial stress, combined with academic and family pressures, contributes to overall academic difficulties, underscoring the importance of financial support and a stable home environment to foster better academic outcomes.

Relationship between the Students' Academic Concerns and the Extent affecting their Academic Performance

Table 3.2 shows a significant relationship between academic concerns (such as performance tasks, written tasks, and major examinations) and their impact on students' academic performance. Pearson correlation coefficients ($r = 0.509$ for performance tasks, $r = 0.513$ for written tasks, and $r = 0.635$ for major examinations) indicate moderate to strong positive correlations, suggesting that as students' academic concerns increase, their academic performance is also affected. The ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) in each case confirm the statistical significance of these relationships.

Studies support these findings as the major stressors in the academic lives of students include academic stress and personal problems such as family issues and financial concerns (Deng et al., 2022; Usman et al., 2019). Under extreme academic pressure, burnout, demotivation, and consequently poor academic performance is seen in students. For instance, financial pressure limits students' access to resources necessary for learning, thus their ability to fully participate in learning (Hamilton et al., 2019). Teaching quality, curriculum, and peer support systems also influence students' academic performance (Kahu & Nelson, 2018; Wentzel, 2022). Therefore, these results underscore the need to offer a nurturing learning environment, resolve individual challenges, and foster good academic practices to improve the students' academic performance.

Relationship between the Students' Family Concerns and the Extent affecting their Academic Performance

Table 3.3 shows that family concerns significantly affect students' academic performance since all of its strong positive correlations with performance tasks ($r = 0.676$), written tasks ($r = 0.597$), and major examinations ($r = 0.614$), respectively ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$), which means that the more students perceive their family concerns as more prevalent, the worse the level of impact on their academic outcomes. Family issues, be it financial stress, emotional pressure, or lack of support, have been quite well documented in literature to be a stressor preventing academic success (Deng et al., 2022; Zakaria, 2023; Hamilton et al., 2019).

A student's potential to perform academically is not only an individualistic function of internal factors, such as motivation and abilities, but also a direct function of the external support that his family environment provides (Alqurashi, 2021). Research also indicates that supportive family backgrounds, including parental engagement and

motivation, boost the performance of students in their academic work (Wang et al., 2022). Conversely, financial struggles, personal stressors, and negative family interactions are some of the challenges that might reduce the attention of students to academic issues and result in poorer academic results (Mudzakir et al., 2024; Subramani & Venkatachalam, 2019). These findings indicate that the issues affecting family performance need to be given priority in improving academic performance. Supportive home environments can help learners overcome academic challenges and enhance well-being, which may translate to better academic performance across different types of academic tasks.

Relationship between the Students' Suicidal Ideation and the Extent affecting their Academic Performance

The data in Table 3.4 show a significant relationship between students' suicidal ideation and the extent to which it affects their academic performance. The positive Pearson correlation coefficients indicate that higher levels of suicidal thoughts are associated with a decline in academic performance across all areas. Specifically, the correlation values for performance tasks (0.470), written tasks (0.394), and major examinations (0.452) suggest moderate to strong relationships. The ($p = 0.00 < 0.05$) for each variable indicate that these relationships are statistically significant, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_{01}). This means that suicidal ideation has a significant impact on students' ability to perform academically. This is evident from the high Pearson correlation values and low p-values, which indicate that students experiencing suicidal thoughts tend to have lower academic performance across these areas.

Similar findings are reported by several studies, which emphasize the negative impact of mental health issues, including anxiety, depression, and suicidal ideation, on students' academic outcomes (Ghorbanpour et al., 2024; Mathewson, 2020). Research by Howard (2019) and Farley et al. (2019) also confirms that mental health challenges, especially in college years, are closely linked to academic difficulties and lower performance.

Personal, family, and financial concerns further compound the struggles students face. For instance, studies by Hamilton et al. (2019) and Usman et al. (2019) show that financial stress can lead to lower grades and fewer opportunities for learning outside of school, while family dynamics can significantly influence a student's academic motivation and performance (Mudzakir et al., 2024). This is consistent with findings from Wentzel (2022), who highlights that positive peer relationships can enhance academic motivation and performance, while negative social influences have the opposite effect.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the data gathered highlights the significant personal challenges faced by students in relation to financial, academic, family, and mental health concerns. The students reported experiencing stress from balancing academic responsibilities with financial pressures, with a composite score indicating that these concerns "often" impact

their well-being. Academic challenges, including pressure to perform well and the anxiety of balancing schoolwork with extracurricular activities, were also significant, often leading to burnout and decreased motivation. Family issues, while less frequently cited as a direct concern, still played a role in affecting students' concentration and motivation to succeed academically. Interestingly, suicidal ideation, although rarely reported, was still present in some students, reflecting the severity of their struggles. The impact of these personal challenges on academic performance is evident in all aspects of students' work. From performance tasks to major examinations, the challenges significantly hinder students' productivity and focus, as shown by the moderate to high correlation between personal issues and academic outcomes. Specifically, financial, academic, family, and mental health concerns were all found to have a statistically significant relationship with students' academic performance, including their written tasks and major examinations. The data underscores the urgent need for support systems to address these personal challenges and enhance students' ability to succeed academically despite their difficulties.

Recommendations

Metro Dumaguete Administration:

1. Strengthen financial aid programs and increase resource allocation to help remove financial burdens from students and divert their attention more significantly toward the academic process.

Guidance Counselors:

2. Increase access to mental health resources and counseling services to aid students who are under a lot of stress and pressure related to academic demands.

Teachers:

3. Implement academic support services like tutoring and study groups to help students who may struggle balancing school works.
4. Establish feedback mechanisms where students can voice their concerns regarding academic pressures and personal challenges, allowing institutions to adapt their support systems accordingly.
5. Faculty are encouraged for regular check-ins to monitor students' workloads and personal challenges for possible early identification of those in need of additional support.

Parents:

6. Encourage parental involvement through workshops that educate families on the way to support their children's educational paths without causing undue pressure.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers showed all the necessary ethical considerations for the entire duration of the study. Since humans were chosen as the study participants, the confidentiality of information was observed. Ensuring the dignity and privacy of participants was also a must. Further, minimizing potential risks to the participants was always observed.

The researchers followed the ethical protocols stipulated in the Ethics Committee of Metro Dumaguete College. Consultation was pursued to ensure the research topic was sound, significant, and ethically correct. The researcher also displayed a non-judgmental attitude during the entire data-gathering process to ensure that censure was avoided. Moreover, the participants signed a consent form and fully understood the risks and benefits of the study being conducted.

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